

An Idea of Modeling Earthquake Prediction System Based On Sensor Network

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Abstract- In this paper we propose an idea of Modeling Earthquake's location and prediction around the world by using modern wireless sensor networking combined with the technology of GPS. The target of this Paper focuses on finding the location and happening time of Earthquake event in the hazard environment. With the information collected from the sensors, we will be able to predict earthquake activities in time series. The process is also demonstrated in OPNET simulation.

Keywords- Wireless Sensor Network, Zigbee, DART, Satellite communication, OPNET

I. Introduction

Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) is an advanced technology and famous with data collection. Since the technology of wireless networks become increasingly matured, wireless sensor network has gradually become a research hotspot^[1]. WSN consists of a number of sensor nodes (few dozens to thousands) with capabilities of storing, processing and relaying sensed data, and also a base station called Sink for further computation^[1]. It has very broad application and great potential value in many areas, such as military and national defense, environmental monitoring, and biomedical, smart homes, remote monitoring in dangerous areas, and so on.

Wireless Sensor Networks were firstly used in military missions.^[3] They are currently deployed in a wide range of civil applications because of overcoming the energy consumption constraint the dimension becomes smaller and smaller. Most of applications require reliable end-to-end data transportation without changing or recharging the battery^[3]. In order to study deployment and performance of Wireless Sensor Networks without much risk in financial resources various network simulators have been developed or extended in this matter^[3].

Area Monitoring is a common application of WSN. In the area monitoring WSN is deployed over a region where some phenomenon can be monitored (Figure 1). When a sensor detects some events, it reports through relays to the base stations. WSN can also find application in monitoring Earth environment.

Figure 1 Satellite based WSN

The work of this paper focuses on detecting the activity of Earthquake. As long as the signals of Earthquake activation are collected from all the sensors distributed on land, coastal area and underwater, data will be processed to locate event center and predict happening time..

II. WSN's Applications in Earthquake Monitoring

Earthquake monitoring is a very tough job because it needs long term and large scale coverage, even though it happens in very short time. So far, there is no way to exactly predict where and when it is going to happen. What we could do is deploy the sensors as many as we can and predict excited moment based on the history data. Subject to low cost and low power consumption of WSN, we will be able to collect vibrant signal generated by the lithosphere movement around Earth.

1. WSN Positioning With GPS

a) GPS Basics

The Global Positioning System (GPS) is a technical marvel made by a group of satellites in earth orbit that transmit precise signals, allowing GPS receivers to calculate and display accurate location, speed, and time information. There are at least 24 operational GPS satellites at all times plus a number of spares. All GPS satellites are synchronized operations so that these repeating signals are transmitted at the same instant. The signals, moving at the speed of light, arrive at a GPS receiver at slightly different time because they are difference in the distances.

A GPS receiver figures out how far away it is from each satellite, based on how much time it takes a broadcast signal to travel from the satellite to the receiver. Since the location of each satellite is know,

the receiver's location can be determined by "Triangulating" the distance from at least 3 satellites as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Location between three spheres

b) Application of GPS Positioning

Today there are so many devices embedded with Global Positioning System. Car navigation system is the most famous application of GPS receivers. It enables public also to access the maps. People use GPS in several circumstances. Survey results of GPS application are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Percentage of GPS usage

Car	37%
Hand Held	28%
Tracking	10%
GIS	8%
Survey	7%
Manufacturing	7%
Vessel Voyage	2%
Military Related	1%

c) WSN with GPS

GPS has become a popular technology of positioning method in the modern life. In the Earthquake monitoring system we can use GPS to find the position of WSN's base station. After collecting the

information of each node, WSN's base station will send information to the control center through satellite relay.

The information of node will be having the Longitude and Latitude information in it (1). GPS will be helpful to give Longitude and Latitude information for both, Nodes & Coordinator point. After having the information of coordinators and Nodes, we will use Halverson Formula (2) and Value equation (3). As the nodes are from all round the world, so we will use distance formula (4) with the radius of earth to find distance in Kilometers (4).

$$\text{Latitude: } 34.0522^\circ \text{ N} \quad \text{Longitude: } 118.2436^\circ \text{ W} \quad (1)$$

$$C = 2 * \arctan \left(\frac{\sqrt{a}}{\sqrt{1+a}} \right) \quad (3)$$

$$A = [\sin^2(\text{Lat}/2) + \cos(\text{Lat } 1) * \cos(\text{Lat } 2) * \sin^2(\text{Longi}/2)] \quad (2)$$

$$d = R * c \quad (4)$$

In WSN by using the GPS Longitude and Latitude Methodology, we can find the distance between to nodes or also can have the distance between Nodes and Coordinators. This can be useful if Earthquake happens in some area of one Node and another Node is located to far area, so from this methodology we can calculate that how far is the affected area from some of the affected areas and can be useful for the positioning of earthquake point. So we will have all the nodes inter and distance between Coordinates in Figure 3.

Fig 3 : WSN nodes (what do you want to say?)

2. Location of Earthquake by using WSN

As the GPS was useful to find the distance between Nodes and their Coordinator all round the world, So the next stage will be how to find that which node is effected and which terminology can be useful for finding the affected area with the help of WSN. We can divide it into two parts.

a) Gathering Information from Nodes

In WSN for the collection of Data from different nodes there are two famous Network methods, Hierarchical and Flat Network method. Following difference and qualities related between Hierarchical & Flat network (Table 2)

Table 2: Difference between Hierarchical & Flat network

Hierarchical Networks	Flat Networks
Data aggregation performed by cluster heads or a leader node.	Data aggregation is performed by different nodes along the multi-hop path.
Even if one cluster head is Failed, still the network may still be operational.	The Failure of sink node may result in the breakdown of entire network.
Lower Latency is involved since sensor node performs short range transmission to the cluster head.	High latency is involved in data transmission to the sink via a multi-hop path.
Routing structure is simple but not necessarily optimal.	Optional routing can be guaranteed with additional overhead.

Multi-hop routing is will be used to communicate data. Sources send data to a collection entity (e.g. gateway): Periodically or on-demand. A sensor node that generates data, based on its sensing mechanisms, if some abnormal activity is occurred in area of Node. This observation will be also based on the historical data according to the mechanism of sensor and Nodes. The collected information will be send to the main station using shortest path and through satellite network (Figure 7).

Figure 4: Data Transmission from Node to Coordinator

b) Position of Node in WSN

As in session (1.b) it is discussed that when more than one satellite find the user location, then there formed the sphere area of each satellite and user will be somewhere inside that spheres (Figure 4). In WSN after receiving and processing the data we have to find the location of Earthquake center. As a number of sensors are connected to Nodes, so same method of GPS satellite sphere will be used to find the exact position of Earthquake effected area. An example of related method shown in (Figure 8). If earthquake is happened somewhere, the data of sensors will be received by all the Nodes near that area, and that point of center will be in between spheres of Node. In (Figure 8) the affected area is in sphere of three Nodes. The basic Equations for all three spheres for calculations are

$$\text{Sphere A: } d_a^2 = (x - x_a)^2 + (y - y_a)^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Sphere B: } d_b^2 = (x - x_b)^2 + (y - y_b)^2 \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Sphere C: } d_c^2 = (x - x_c)^2 + (y - y_c)^2 \quad (7)$$

We can get the X and Y axis of the effected point in spheres from (d) & (e)

$$Y = V_b (X_b - X_c) - V_a (X_b - X_a) / (Y_a - Y_b) (X_b - X_c) - (Y_c - Y_b) (X_b - X_c) \quad (8)$$

$$X = Y (Y_a - Y_b) - V_b / (X_b - X_c) \quad (9)$$

Figure 5: Position geometry

c) Data processing

(How to process sum of the data from large amount of nodes?)

You can mention about how to filter out the correlative data because you just need three, but you should clarify how to use those data.)

3. Prediction of Earthquake happen Time (in this sector, you don't need give the results but the some equations)

a) Introduction to general prediction algorithms (rewriting the below)

b) Data processing of multiple node composition (rewriting the below)

c) Prediction algorithm of Earthquake data (rewriting the below)

III. Simulation of WSN in Opnet

1. Introduction to WSN of Zigbee system

Zigbee, is known as IEEE 802.15.4 standard, a category of the IEEE 802 family. However unlike Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, Zigbee was developed for low power consumption^[17]. Zigbee technology is an ideal choice to be widely deployed due to the low cost implementation. Zigbee is also used in medical field for monitoring the patients^[19].

Since Zigbee is low rate and short range wireless technology with star, tree and mesh topology, and global certification assuring interoperability. Thus it has good application for wireless sensor network and has been rapid development. Current location based services are attracting people's attention. The Zigbee system has very good potential commercial value, especially in earthquake prediction and location applications.

Table3: (replace this table and put some parameters and applications of Zigbee)

	ZigBee	Wi-Fi (802.11n)	Bluetooth
Data Rate	20,40 and 250 Kbps	up to 150Mbps	1Mbps
Range	10-3000m	70-250m	10-100m
Frequency	868MHz, (EU) 900-928MHz, (NA) 2.4GHz (WL)	2.4 & 5 GHz	2.4GHz
Complexity	Low	High	High
Battery Life (days) [3]	100 to > 1000	1 to 5	1 to 7

The applications and specifications listed in the table show that Zigbee is very good choice of WSN applied in earthquake prediction and location. [?].

2. Introduction to OPNET Simulation

The OPNET Modeler is commercial network simulation software by Opnet Technologies. A Graphical User Interface (GUI) supports the scenarios and configurations of a network system development. Three hierarchical levels for configuration are defined: network level creates the protocols under network topology; node level defines the behavior of nodes in controlling the data flow between different functional elements inside the node; process level describes the underlying protocols represented by finite state machines (FSMs), which are created with states and transitions between states. The source code is programmed in C/C++. The analysis of simulated data is supported by a variety of built-in functions.

OPNET develops specialized modules in a library style, like Wireless, UMTS, etc. Additional modules are contributed by the University Program. For mobility models, the random waypoint, arbitrary trajectories and mobility can update from external sources via the HLA (Higher Layer Architecture).

a) OPNET Libraries

The model libraries developed by OPNET supplier can be used to simulate and analyze major networking technologies and communication protocols. These libraries are composed of some typical

systems and modules used to generate different network models. A network model consists of many software objects that correspond to actual devices, computers, and links of interest. The behavior of these objects is controlled by models of the devices, applications, communication protocols, and links. *OPNET Modeler* includes extensive libraries of popular and emerging networking technologies and communication protocols, such as TCP/IP, hypertext transfer protocol, or HTTP, open shortest path first routing (OSPF), asynchronous transfer mode (ATM), frame relay, IP-QOS, 802.11-16, Wi-Fi, and WiMAX..

b) Zigbee design in Opnet (just take something about Zigbee from OPNET and explain how to use it to built the WSN)

Zigbee designed for Wireless Sensor Network (WSN) can be simulated in OPNET. In case of world-wide network we can design Zigbee on world map and can make cluster network (Figure 11).

There are three different Zigbee device types that operate on the Zigbee layers, and available in OPNET:

The Coordinator: There is one, and only one, Zigbee coordinator in each network to act as the router to other networks. It is designed to initialize the network, store information about the network, select the appropriate channel, and granting access for other devices to connect to its network.

Router: Zigbee routers are used to transmit data from other devices and it is also able to have other nodes attached to it, such as a router or an end device. These other nodes are referred to as child nodes. Routers need lesser memory than a Zigbee coordinator, and require lesser manufacturing costs. It can operate in all topologies and in some cases it can act as a limited coordinator.

End Device: End devices are capable of talking in the network but it cannot relay data from other devices. It requires even less memory, i.e. no flash, very little ROM and RAM. This device talks only to a network coordinators and routers. An end device does not have the ability to have other nodes connect to its network through the end device, as it must be connected to the network through either a router, or directly to the coordinator. In more advanced mesh network topologies each device can communicate with other devices irrelevant of their types.

Figure 6: Zigbee Topologies in OPNET

c) Data Gathering in WSN (rewrite below text to Earthquake scenario in OPNET)

The process of grouping the sensor nodes in a densely deployed large-scale sensor network is known as clustering. The intelligent way to combine and compress the data belonging to a single cluster is known as data aggregation in cluster based environment.

For the Earthquake Prediction system, the WSN is also deployed on Large-scale round the world and also clustered. Aggregator node plays important role in establishing secure and accurate exchange of data. An aggregator node can compute the sum, average, minimum or maximum of the data from its children sensors, and send the aggregation results to a higher-level aggregator. WSN can choose its aggregators dynamically according to their power remnant to optimize the total power consumption of the aggregation.

Generally, two methods can be used for secure data aggregation in WSN:

(1) Hop by Hop Encrypted Data Aggregation: Data is encrypted by the sensing nodes and decrypted by aggregator nodes. The aggregator nodes then aggregate the data and encrypt the aggregation result again. At last the sink node gets the final encrypted aggregation result and decrypts it. This technique is implemented by using these steps, (a) Aggregating the data should be done inside the network. (b) After aggregation of data there should be authentication of data to be done to achieve integrity of aggregation results.

(2) End to End Encrypted Data Aggregation: In this type of data aggregation intermediate nodes haven't decryption keys and they can only do aggregations on the encrypted data. End-to-end privacy needs to

establish a network-wide key between the sink and all the sensor nodes. It provides end-to-end privacy between sensor nodes and the sink.

Now the whole system will be divided into three levels (Figure 9)

(1) Sensor Network: Have all sensor cloud which receives data from all sensors that are deployed in area.

(2) Cluster heads: As WSN will be deployed all over world, so it will be done by cluster network design. All sensor networks are connected to their Cluster Head for forwarding information out of network.

(3) Satellites Gateways: For wide broadcast, satellite network is connected with the Cluster Heads, which can receive data from different cluster heads and will broadcast to main control center.

Figure 7: Satellite based WSN system

IV. Conclusion

As it's the combination of two latest technologies Wireless Sensor Networking and GPS, So it's a new and very useful technique for positioning a target or effected place or object. As Wireless sensor network

is used for different monitoring systems for environmental hazards, so this technique of Wireless sensor Network with combination of GPS and Sphere axis methodology to work for one of the biggest hazard Earthquake/Tsunami will be good to take WSN one step more further towards progress. In future with the improvement in WSN Protocols and GNSS satellite networking , this project can be further explored and more benefits can be gained in Positioning and Monitoring of some of the deadly Natural Environment Hazards.

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